

INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF THE PRESIDENTIAL AND SPECIALIZED SCHOOLS BASED ON NEW PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. *The article focuses on increasing the effectiveness of the activities of the President, creative and specialized schools established in our country on the basis of new pedagogical technologies, as well as teaching in communicative situations promoted by the disciplines of functional linguistics, psycholinguistics, and methodology in the process of teaching foreign languages, organizing the educational activities of students in cooperation ideas and considerations about the need to include innovative technologies in the process of using emotional influence tools that correspond to life needs and communicative situations in language teaching are presented with examples.*

Keywords: *pedagogical technologies, functional linguistics, psycholinguistics, communicative situations, interactive method, brainstorming.*

All reforms aimed at improving the efficiency of higher and secondary special educational institutions and schools specializing in training gifted children in our republic are undoubtedly aimed at improving the methods of teaching foreign languages and implementing modern pedagogical technologies in the educational process. Implementation of such a social order in practice, in the process of teaching foreign languages, naturally puts before scientists the task of developing and introducing new pedagogical technologies. After all, the development of our society is determined by the degree to which the intellectual abilities of our future generation specialists are formed.

In this regard, on September 9, 2019, President ShavkatMiromonovichMirziyoev on additional measures to further improve the activities of the Agency for the Development of Creativity and Specialized Schools in the presence of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan signed the decree on the establishment of the agency.

Currently, 16 schools with all conditions are operating in the Agency system. In particular, in 4 presidential schools, 9 creative schools and 3 specialized schools, 3095 students are receiving in-depth knowledge in various fields of science.

Today, 4 of the 14 presidential schools planned to be established in our republic are operating in Tashkent, Nukus, Khiva, Namangan, Samarkand and other regions. [piima.uz].

It can be seen that in such schools today, functional linguistics, psycholinguistics, methodical sciences promote the teaching of foreign languages in communicative situations, cooperative organization of students' educational activities, and language teaching. issues of using emotional means of influence corresponding to life needs and communicative situations make it necessary to introduce innovative technologies into this process. Therefore, the creation of a methodical system of using the functional, communicative, and emotional capabilities of a foreign language, thereby increasing the effectiveness of education, is promoted as one of the

urgent problems of today. This issue, as an innovative pedagogical technology, is currently attracting the attention of scientists all over the world.

A new approach to the process of teaching foreign languages in presidential, creative and specialized schools, organizing the lesson process on the basis of innovative technologies, using interactive methods that shape the linguistic and communicative competence of students in this regard, the above allowed in the traditional teaching process there is no doubt that there will be a new education aimed at eliminating the shortcomings.

From this point of view, retraining of professors and teachers working in the educational system of our republic (higher, secondary, vocational, presidential, creative and specialized schools, general education schools) and strict control of training results, in this regard, it is necessary to reconsider the issues of increasing the material and moral responsibility of the responsible persons.

In recent years, many new concepts such as "Innovative pedagogy", "Innovative technologies", "Interactive methods and methods", "New pedagogical technologies" have entered the educational process. In this regard, Russian scientists V.P. Beshpal'ko, V.I. Zagvezinsky, V.A. Slastinin and others, Uzbek scientists K.Abdullaeva, Sh.Abdullaeva, N.Kh. In the studies of A.Kh.Qasimov and F. Khalikova, detailed theoretical and practical ideas about modernizing the educational process, new pedagogical technologies and their pedagogical and psychological foundations have been collected.

In almost all of the above-mentioned studies, the proposed innovative ideas are characterized by their application in the process of teaching social and humanitarian sciences. That is, the methods and methods of organizing the activities of people who think and speak the Uzbek language in interactive ways, their curiosity, and their activities aimed at learning new knowledge are discussed.

So, are there opportunities to use such interactive methods and innovative ideas in the process of teaching foreign languages? In order to answer such a question, first of all, we need to clearly know the goal and final results expected from teaching foreign languages, ie. Not to train future specialists only in the foreign language system, which is envisaged in our traditional education, but in which they have vital, we should not forget that the main goal is to form and improve communication skills and competencies in various communicative situations that match their professional needs.

Currently, we can see different definitions of the concept of new pedagogical technology:

Pedagogical technology is a model of the educational process that requires the design and organization of the educational process, provides for the complete and detailed organization of the teaching activity of the teacher and the learning activity of students (Monakhov).

Pedagogical technology is a method of application of personal, intellectual, methodological tools used to achieve pedagogical goals. (Clarine).

Russian scientist N.F. Talyzina defines pedagogical technology as "determining reasonable ways to achieve the specified educational goal."

According to I.Ya.Lerner, pedagogical technology is a system of results aimed at conscious mastering as a clear goal reflected in students' educational actions.

It can be seen that the pedagogical technology envisages the organization of the educational process as a design based on the set goals and topics. Academician V.P. Beshpalko (pedagogical technology) describes this situation as a project of the process of student

personality formation, which can guarantee pedagogical success depending on the teacher's skills.

According to scientists R. Ishmukhammedov, A. Abdukadirov, A. Pardaev, who have researched the practical application of innovative pedagogical technologies, pedagogical technology is an integrated process in a clear sequence, which is based on the needs of the student (or student) and is aimed at one goal. is a pedagogical process aimed at providing a directed, well-planned and guaranteed result.

In this regard, the well-known specialist N. Saidahmedov analyzes the definitions of several scientists and points out that for a certain period of time, pedagogical technology has been considered as the implementation of the educational process with the help of technical means.

Therefore, pedagogical technology is the process of implementing pedagogical procedures designed based on the needs and capabilities of learners, implemented in a certain sequence and order, based on specific goals, and guaranteeing the achievement of the final result.

In the pedagogical literature, the concept of "innovation" is defined as a previously unknown and unrecorded method and method, a result, a developing theory and a pedagogical reality that leads to a pedagogical innovation in teaching, training and education.

One of the important conditions for applying the innovative pedagogical process to the methodology of teaching foreign languages is the student's self-control and self-mobilization in acquiring speech actions. One of its most important conditions is the formation and development of communication and cognitive activities of students based on communicative-functional, emotional-cognitive principles, as a result of which, it is envisaged to form and develop students' communicative competence in a foreign language, that is, the potential for communication.[6:333-339].

It is necessary to create a unique technology for each lesson, subject, that is, pedagogical technology in the educational process is an active learning process, which is directed to a specific goal, pre-designed and guaranteed result based on the communicative needs of the student. is a pedagogical process aimed at giving. It is necessary to take into account the unique side of the teacher's educational material, the communicative situation in explaining it and strengthening it in the independent work process, the possibilities of using technical means of education and all audio-visual, extralinguistic and emotional means of influence. Only then can the desired, guaranteed result be achieved.

In the process of teaching, students are treated as individuals, various pedagogical technologies and modern methods are used to enable them to think independently, freely, to research, to approach each issue creatively, to feel responsibility, to carry out scientific research, analysis, scientific and practical work. to make effective use of additional literature, and most importantly, to increase their interest in reading, science, and their chosen profession.

All new pedagogical technologies leading to the improvement of teaching efficiency help students to form logical, mental, creative, critical, independent thinking skills, develop communicative competence and abilities, become competitive, mature specialists in their field, and are necessary for specialists. should lead to the formation of professional qualities.

The difference between a person and other creatures is that he sets a goal for himself and moves towards it. Any goal arises from the need of a particular person, social group or nation. Since man is a biosocial being, he has a social need along with his biological needs.

Social needs are needs such as thinking, exchanging ideas, learning, working, having fun, loving and being loved, which arise under the influence of social development.

The design of new technologies and their use in the educational process is based on certain laws. These principles express the unique aspects of pedagogical technology and show the different aspects of the methodology. In other words, they can be called principles of pedagogical technologies.

By the principles of pedagogical technology, we understand the general standards, rules and requirements to be followed in order to achieve high results in the implementation of the designed educational process. According to the conducted analytical-synthetic studies, the principles of pedagogical technologies are fundamentally different from didactic principles and embody important quality indicators.

Uzbek pedagogic scientist N. Sayidahmedov suggests following principles when applying new pedagogical technologies:

1. The principle of integrity. When creating a technology project, it is necessary to take into account that all elements of the pedagogical system are within the framework of interaction and interdependence;

2. Pedagogical technology envisages the preliminary design of the educational process and the practical implementation of this project at the next stage;

3. The principle of guaranteeing the final result.

New pedagogical technologies promote the need for a new approach and organization to the design of the educational process based on the new educational system, content, curriculum, textbooks. The actual textbooks and manuals that are used in the process of teaching foreign languages, created and republished in the second half of the last century, firstly, because they are intended for students of the Russian language, do not correspond to our national mentality, and secondly, they are not adapted to the communicative needs of students, emotional- it did not meet today's requirements due to the fact that it was not incorporated into the cognitive methodical system.

Therefore, first of all, the idea of expanding and modernizing the educational content and its structure, in particular, including not only knowledge, skills and competence, but also the idea of intercultural communication, experience of creative activity, and relationships with the environment, which make up universal human culture, is on the agenda. being transposed.

Pedagogical technologies can be divided into the following types according to the role of the student in the educational process and the attitude of the pedagogue towards students:

- a) Authoritarian technology. In this, the pedagogue is the main subject of the educational control process, and the student participates only as an object. It is based on stifling the freedom of students, forced teaching, stifling the initiative and conducting the educational process with rigor. In the process of such teaching, the student learns the language material not for voluntary mastery, but only because he is afraid of the teacher.

- b) Didactocentric technologies - characterized by ignoring the personality of the student. In this too, there are subject-object relations, and the main goal is to form a person without leaving the limits of discipline. In this technology, the student's personality and free expression are not taken into account.

- v) Person-oriented technologies - in the center of which lies the creation of all conditions for the development of the student's personality, helping to manifest his educational and

educational potential. In this case, the student becomes not only a subject, but a subject with priority. It becomes the goal of the educational system. Such technologies are also called "anthropocentric technologies".

Person-oriented technologies are anthropocentric, humanistic and psychotherapeutic, all-round free, creatively developed personality and they are reflected in the technologies of teaching communication in a foreign language.

g) Humanitarian technologies - by its very nature, provides comprehensive help and support to the student. It aims to respect the personality of the student, to help him develop his abilities, and compulsory education is denied. In teaching foreign languages, this technology is reflected in the teaching of communication through the means of emotional influence.

d) Collaborative technologies - it promotes the ideas of democracy, equality and is based on subject-subject in teacher-student relationship. The teacher and the student work together based on the purpose and content of education and evaluate their activities together. Today, this technology is reflected in the communication tasks in pairs and groups, in the project teaching technology.

e) Technology of free education - in this the student is given the opportunity to work freely in all directions. In the process of choosing the type of activity, the student manifests himself from the point of view of the subject and achieves the result not through external influence, but through internal aspirations and needs. Such technology is useful in the formation of students' communicative competence in the process of teaching communication in a foreign language.

According to the methods of using pedagogical technologies, they can be divided into traditional and non-traditional technologies. Traditional educational technology - intended for a certain period of time, the educational process is carried out more by the activity of the teacher, using the traditional form of teaching, methods and a set of educational tools. the goal is achieved. Today, such technology does not meet the modern requirements of teaching foreign languages because the teaching material and teaching methods and methods do not match the communicative needs of students and communicative situations.

Non-traditional educational technology - all innovative teaching methods and methods that are intended for a certain period of time and guarantee the intended goal and result of educational work, taking into account that the student should be at the center of the educational process. includes.

Non-traditional educational technology differs from traditional educational technology in that educational activities are organized in cooperation, thereby creating conditions for the development of students' cognitive abilities, special attention is paid to their independent work, cognitive activities have an inquisitive and creative character. The lesson structure will be variable.

Non-traditional educational technologies are mainly used to organize and manage students' collaborative learning activities, teach ways to enter into communication, ensure reproducibility of mastering, and integrate skills and competencies into one system. formative and improving, in this process, it is an innovative technology that directs students to independent research.

The modeling method is to create a condensed and simplified view of the events and processes that occur in real life and society, and involves students' personal participation in them

and acquisition of communication skills through activities. Its main goal is to ensure the direct participation of students in acquiring knowledge, thereby increasing the efficiency of the educational process. Pedagogical technologies based on communicative situations ("Charkhpalak", "Cluster", "Boomerang", "Bahs", "Discussion") and role-playing games can be included. Methodical literature describes the system of methods for educational technologies as follows:

The technology of "Collaborative teaching" shown in the table also includes the technology of "modeling" and "research". Because the modeling of the educational process organized through games, as well as the problem situation, the research technology that involves designing and teaching also envisages working in mutual cooperation of students. Therefore, the technology of "Modeling" and "Research" should be considered as a component of "Collaborative teaching". Uzbek scientists K.Abdullaeva, N.Kh. Avliyokulov, B.Ziyomammedov, J.G. Yoldoshev and the technologies organized in the cooperation of students, such as debate, round discussion, "Zig-zag", "Orgamchik tori" in methodical literature. It is described in detail in the researches of N.Saidahmedov, A.Kh. Qasimov and Sh.Kholikova and others, and it is mainly intended to teach the written expression of thought in the teaching of social sciences. At the moment, they do not pay attention to the issue of matching the studied material to the students' communicative needs and communication situations.

In conclusion, the President, creative and cooperative teaching technologies in specialized schools can give effective results in organizing and strengthening independent work of students on the subject in teaching communication in a foreign language. These are carried out through various games that involve performing communicative tasks, problem solving, project implementation, and mastering speech acts in pairs or groups. This technology, first of all, is organized in an unconventional way, and secondly, it is a component of the technologies described above, with the use of game elements, emotional influence tools, to work in pairs and groups, to conduct research, to complete a project. is characterized. Pedagogical experience has shown that the use of interactive methods and pedagogical technologies in teaching foreign languages is an important factor in improving the effectiveness of the lesson and confirmed that the results are guaranteed.

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